

HOW PRACTICE OF CUSTOMARY MARRIAGE IS NAVIGATING UNCHARTED WATERS OF THE LAW IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Customary marriage laws, profoundly entrenched in tradition and culture, have for extended periods of time served as a pivot for shaping marital unions in many African societies, particularly in Nigeria. For any system of marriage to be valid under customary law, its nature must conform to the prevailing customs and practices of the tribe where the bride comes from, like in private international law; the rule *lex loci celebrationis* i.e. the law of the place where the marriage is celebrated applies to such a customary marriage. This criterion is an essential validity amongst other things, in deciding whether or not a customary marriage has taken place. Thus, customary law governs the character and incidents of that system of marriage and no single uniform system of the law prevails throughout Nigeria. Essentially, customary marriage possesses three main features of customary law; it is unwritten, it is a mirror of accepted usage and wherever it applies, its rules may change with time. This is attributable to unwritten customs and traditions passed down through generations and recognized by the communities as binding. This paper acknowledges that customary law practice, in its sphere of operation, admits changes of its rules, which are elastic in its formation and features, while ensuring that customary marriage laws align with contemporary values and global legal trends. The authors argued that customary law marriages have evolved with contemporary challenges of the times. Nowadays, without evidence of payment of bride price or handing over of the bride to the groom's family, where the parties to a marriage are adults with requisite capacities and can produce evidence to substantiate their intentions, Nigerian courts readily accord the status of customary law marriage on

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them, provided the parties are persons of repute and have substantially lived together as husband and wife by cohabitation.

Introduction

In spite of the prevailing application of western culture and the faith-based religions in Nigeria, The substantial number of marriages contracted are in accordance with customary law. In fact, customary marriages prefaced two other forms of marriage; statutory and Islamic marriages in Nigeria. As the name implies, customary law consists of customs accepted by members of a community as binding among them. There are three ways of creating the status of marriage in Nigeria: by customary law, Moslem law and statutory law. The first two classes are polygamous while the third is monogamous. Each of the three classes has different legal incidents and effects.

Customary Marriage

Customary law marriage is a union between the families of two individuals involved in a marital relationship. It is a form of social contract between the two families. A particular customary marriage must be attached to a specific ethnic group in Nigeria. By virtue of the nature of the Nigerian society, ethnic customary law is unwritten; invariably the mode of conducting customary marriage is unwritten as well. Therefore, there are several such customary law systems in Nigeria, each ethnic

group having its own separate system. Even within a particular tribe like the Yorubas of the South Western part of Nigeria, there exists several sub-ethnic units, although there are certain rules of customary law that are common to all Yoruba areas in Nigeria. But the details of requirements of such marriage vary from one social formation or locality to another. Ijalaiye¹ stated that settled and doubtful requirements exist when considering capacity to contract a valid customary law marriage. He argued that settled requirements to be satisfied in order for a person in Nigeria to contract a valid customary law marriage include; both parties must have attained the age of puberty; the woman must not be married; and the parties must not be related within the prohibited degrees of relationship. The jurist further provided that doubtful requirements include physical fitness; social status and nationality of the parties. However, the Court of Appeal in *Nsirim v. Nsirim*², laid down what may be considered the broad principles of a valid customary law marriage in Nigeria. They are as follows:

(a) The parties to a customary marriage must possess the capacity under that law to marry each other;

¹D. A. Ijalaye, 1967. Capacity to Marry under Nigerian Customary Law, *The Nigerian Bar Journal (Annual Law*

Review) vol. VIII: 20- 25.

²(2002) 3 NWLR (Pt.755) 697; (2002) 2 S.C (Pt.1) 47

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(b) There must be payment of dowry or bride price which is a gift or payment. It may be in money, natural produce and any other kind of property. This must be paid to the parent or guardian of the bride. It must be paid on account of a marriage of a female person and it must be for marriage which is intended or has taken place; and

(c) There must be a ceremony of marriage and the handing over of the woman to the man's family.³

With the varieties of customs amongst the diverse ethnic groups in Nigeria, there appears to be peculiar requirements for marriage in the respective ethnicities concerned. It is however instructive to note that the court has a duty to consider the overall acts performed and subsequently decide the acts that have legal significance and therefore essential to the validity of the marriage.⁴ A major challenge however is that customary marriages are not usually recorded and it is consequently often difficult in certain cases, to determine whether or not parties to alleged marriages have actually complied with all the requirements for validity.⁵

For any system of marriage to be valid under customary law, its nature must conform to the prevailing customs and practices of the tribe where the bride comes from, like in private international law; the rule *lex loci celebrationis* i.e. the law of the place where the marriage is celebrated applies to such a customary marriage. It should be noted that the above criteria are important in deciding whether a customary marriage has taken place. Evidently, in some instances it becomes an issue and the courts have to decide its existence by reference to the above criteria.⁶ In *Lydia Adepeju v. Isaac Adereti*⁷ it was held that it was very important that a customary marriage should be properly proved when it became an issue in the case and that the best proof must come from a person who witnessed the marriage ceremony or took part in it or from the parent of the woman to whom dowry was paid or who gave the woman away in marriage. However, customary law governs the character and incidents of that system and no single uniform system of the law prevails throughout Nigeria.⁸

³See per Onolaja J.C.A. at pp. 167-168. See also *Agbeja v. Agbeja* (1985) 3 NWLR (pt.II) 11.

⁴Jadesola Akande, LL. B (Hons.) Ph. D (London), Professor, Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, University of Lagos, Akoka, 'Legal Problems of Converting a Customary Law Marriage into a Statutory Marriage.': 7- 12 @ 7, being a paper presented at the National Conference on Marriage Laws in Nigeria, held at the Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 1981.

⁵ibid

⁶See NIALS Dictionary of African Customary Laws Edited by Epiphany Azinge, SAN and Oluchi Nwakaego Azoro (Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies) 2013 ISBN: 978-978-8407-85-0 Printed by NIALS PRESS, Supreme Court Complex, Three Arms Zone, Abuja.

⁷(1961) WRNLR 154.

⁸See A.K. Ajisafe: *Law & Customs of the Yorubas*. See also the report of the Integration of Customary and Modern

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Ekundare⁹ observed that in certain States, registration of customary marriages occurred although the registration allowed the parties to prove their status, but it is not a pre-requisite for the validity of a customary law marriage. It is instructive to note that some local governments have bye laws for the registration of customary law marriages.¹⁰ Some bye laws make registration of customary marriages compulsory and prescribe a penalty for failure to register such marriages¹¹ within a specified period after the celebration of marriage. The Act¹² provides that every customary marriage is to be registered within 60 days in the area court or customary court where the marriage was contracted. The Act¹³ further reiterates the requirement for registration within 60 days alongside a list required by the Chief Registrar, which list specifies information relating to the bride and groom.

In *Sulaimon Owolabi Salaudeen v The Secretary of State for the Home Department*,¹⁴ the issue for determination was whether a proxy marriage

contracted under native law and custom in Nigeria was duly registered as prescribed by Nigerian law and whether it was therefore a valid marriage for the purpose of Regulation 7 of the Immigration (European Economic Area) Regulations 2006.¹⁵ In that case, there was an application for a residence card in Europe relying on the proof of a valid marriage which took place according to Nigerian native law and custom. The appellant relied on documents which purportedly demonstrated that a valid marriage took place in Nigeria on 28 June, 2012 and was thereafter registered on 13 August, 2012. Relying amongst other things on the Court of Appeal's decision in *Awuku v SSHD*,¹⁶ it was clear that the general rule under the law of England and Wales is that formal validity of a marriage is governed by the law of the country where the marriage was celebrated. The tribunal found that the First-tier Tribunal decision erred in law and the decision was re-made. The appeal was therefore allowed on European Law grounds on 14 May, 2019.

Legal Systems held at Ibadan in August, 1964 and Conference on Local Courts and Customary Law in Africa held at Dar es Salaam in 1963; Park, A.E.W.: *The Sources of Nigerian Law*, London, Sweet & Maxwell, 1963;

Onwudinjoh v. Onwudinjoh (1957-58) 11 ERLR 1. See also, *the case of the Matter of Caveat Filed by D.O. Edebiri* (1964) MNL 95. Also *Registrar of Marriages v. Igbinomwanhia* Suit No. B/16M/72 (unreported) High Court, Benin, August 5, 1972.

⁹R. O. Ekundare, *Marriage and Divorce under Yoruba Customary Law* 1969 p. 79.

¹⁰Fourth Schedule to the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended).

¹¹For instance the Birth, Deaths etc. (Compulsory Registration) Act Cap B9 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004.

¹²*ibid* Section 30.

¹³*ibid* Section 42, specifies information relating to the bride and groom such as their full names, marital status, occupation, age, state of origin, place of residence, nationality, name of the person who consented to the Marriage and his relationship with the bride/ groom.

¹⁴Tribunal Decisions- EA/ 12934/ 2016, before Upper Tribunal Judge Canavan

¹⁵UK Statutory Instrument 2006 No. 1003.

¹⁶(2017) ECWA Civ 178.

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Essentially, customary marriage possesses three main features of customary law; it is unwritten, it must be a mirror of accepted usage and wherever it applies, its rules may change with time. In view of the fact that customary law admits changes of its rules, customary marriage as well is elastic in its formation and features, therefore, while it is essential that the bride must be handed over by her family to the groom upon the celebration of the marriage so that both parties would live as husband and wife in the matrimonial home. However, the rules of customary law marriage permit non-cohabitation of the spouse provided they are adults and they intend to live as husband and wife, the validity of such a marriage cannot be impugned on the ground of cohabitation. Therefore, what the customary law requires is the will of the parties to live as husband and wife for life, whether or not both of them are domicile in the same locality.

Essentials of Customary Marriage

In Nigeria, there is diversity of customary law systems providing divergent patterns of customary marriages, however, certain fundamental principles and essentials are common to all these systems. These elements must be present before a marriage can exist, this is because in spite of its flexibility, customary law draws a distinction between a man and woman who are merely living together and couples who

are actually married. Under customary marriage system, a man has the capacity to take as many wives as he pleases. Although at a given moment, the fact that he has only one wife does not affect the character of the marriage, for all intents and purposes the capacity to take more wives is retained. It is for this reason that it is said that customary marriage is potentially polygamous and available only to those who are normally subject to a system of customary law.¹⁷ Notwithstanding the latitude of the man to marry many wives, each union is intended to last for life. There are three essential requirements of Yoruba customary marriage as presently evolved. These are parental consent, the parties' consent and most crucially the payment of the dowry. Cohabitation after the payment of the bride price or dowry is a feature of customary marriage but it is to be noted that once the dowry is paid the woman becomes a bride even though cohabitation takes place at a much later time.

Parental Consent

In Nigerian societies, the parents of the prospective spouses have significant roles to play in the marriage of their children. Customary marriage is not a union between two individuals but between the two families. The seal of approval to the union comes from the two families. As customary law adapts to changes, so does customary marriage, thus parental consent is now subtly whittles down depending on the

¹⁷*Savage v McFoy* (1909) Ren. 505 @ 508; *Fonseca v Pasoman* (1958) WNLR 41.

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age and social status of the spruces. It is the consent of the parents of the bride that is of paramount importance to the validity of the marriage, since the marriage is conducted in the home of the parents of the bride. While parents have the right to withhold their consent, this is not common in practice. In some States of the Federation there has been legislation for judicial intervention on the proof by the couple that such parental consent has been unreasonably withheld.¹⁸

Consent of the Parties

Under customary law, consent of both parties was not mandatory to establish a valid marriage i.e. it was not a condition precedent. This is further buttressed by the practice of child betrothal/ child marriage, which was a common phenomenon in many communities in Nigeria including the Yorubas.¹⁹ However, in accordance with the changing feature of customary law, modern practice demands that mutual consent is required to establish a valid marriage,²⁰ as a party that does not consent is entitled to seek relief in a customary court.

Bride Price

Generally, bride price is culturally regarded as a respectful gesture towards women and their families. It symbolizes gratitude to the bride's

family, the acknowledgement of the groom's commitment and fosters familial bonds. Some scholars however argue that there exists a frequent reinforcement of harmful gender norms which perceive women as commodities involved in transactional exchanges between families. In certain instances, whether or not the bride price paid is high, some women are subjected to the increased pressure to remain in their marriages, irrespective of the quality or safety of such unions.

Customary law requires a mandatory payment of bride price as an essential requirement to the validity of the marriage. The giving of a specified amount of money by the family of the groom and the receipt of that money by the family of the bride legitimizes the union. Like modern contract, the arrangement represents offer and acceptance. The payment of bride price is symbolic; the amount does not represent the true value of the bride in the society. This explains why we have divergent ranges of bride price among the communities. In recent times, most families of the bride receive a token amount as the bride price as they believe that the idea of exchanging their daughter for monetary considerations epitomizes a sales transaction. Thus, many families accept other gifts in lieu of

¹⁸See Section 5, Western Marriage, Divorce and Custody Adoptive Bye Laws Order 1958. See *Okpanum v. Okpanum* (1972) ECSR 561. *Mayaki & Anor. v. Alhaji Nda* 1 SMC (2002) 101. *Osamwoyi v. Osamwoyi* (1978) 10 SC 1

¹⁹A. I. Olatunbosun, 'Addressing the Phenomenon of Child Marriage in Nigeria' in *Ife Psychologia*, an International

Journal, vol. 9: 2 (Ife Centre for Psychological Studies, Nigeria & University of Cape Coast, Ghana): 159 – 169.

²⁰E. I. Nwogugu, 2011, *Family Law in Nigeria*, Revised Edition (Heinemann Educational Books (Nigeria) Plc. 45.

See also *Osamawonyi v Osamawonyi* (1972) 10 SC 1.

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the full amount. These various gifts accompanying the specified bride price by the groom's family to the bride and her relations at the marriage ceremony does not constitute bride price and as such are not refundable upon the dissolution of the marriage, the bride price is however refundable.

Refund of bride price is a common customary requirement for dissolving a customary marriage and this symbolizes a formal termination of the union. Among the Igbos, the process is referred to as 'Izuchi' ahia nwanyi' and it connotes returning the exact amount paid during a family meeting. Under moslem law, applicable in Northern Nigeria, a woman seeking divorce referred to as 'Khul'i' may return the dowry and courts allow for flexibility. In *Usman v Umar*,²¹ a Sharia Court permitted a wife to pay seventy thousand naira (#70, 000) as refund of dowry, instead of the required three hundred and twenty thousand naira (#320, 000) on the basis of economic hardship claims tendered.

Oni²² reviewed the Court of Appeal decision in *Ezeaku v Okonkwo*²³ which considered dissolution of marriage contracted under customary law. The issue for determination was whether a sworn affidavit was sufficient to dissolve a marriage contracted under customary

law, as to deprive a spouse right of inheritance. Oni aligned himself with the Court of Appeal that the trial court erred in law while considering the essential elements for a valid dissolution of customary marriage. He noted that customary marriages can only be dissolved by the court and further reiterated that such marriages can also be dissolved either unilaterally or by mutual consent, subject to the refund of dowry. The author submitted that in the instant case, there was no proof of dissolution of marriage between the appellant and Okonkwo and that the fact that they lived apart for 17 years as contained in the affidavit (exhibit 'A') was not sufficient moral or legal justification to conclude that the said marriage had ceased to exist prior to the demise of the deceased. The case of *Ezeaku v Okonkwo*²⁴ expressly revealed that marriage whether statutory or customary is not dissolved by effluxion of time. It is not enough for either party to a customary marriage to suo motu bring it to an end by merely deposing to an affidavit to that effect. It is important to note also that a woman who is the wife of a man under customary law does not divorce the man merely by leaving him and staying with another man while bearing children for that other man.²⁵

²¹*Musa Usman v Aisha Umar* (2023) Unreported, Sharia Court Kaduna.

²²B. A. Oni, 2015. Dissolution of Marriage Contracted under Customary Law in Nigeria: Comments on *Ezeaku v Okonkwo*, US- China Law Review 12: 624- 631.

²³(2012) All FWLR pt 654 at p. 128.

²⁴ibid

²⁵*Lawal Osula v Lawal Osula* (1993) 2 NWLR pt. 274 at 158.

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A trending occurrence in dissolution of marriage cases is where petitioners for dissolution of marriage are the very same persons who actually deserted their matrimonial home, but yet attempt to cleverly flip the script and run to court after the parties to the marriage have lived apart for a continuous period of at least three (3) years preceding the presentation of the petition, to seek for dissolution of the union relying on desertion as a ground for dissolution in accordance with the Matrimonial Causes Act.²⁶ In *Zaccheus v Zaccheus*,²⁷ the issue for determination was whether a petitioner who deserted the matrimonial home can rely on desertion as a ground for dissolution. The court noted that the petitioner was trying to be clever by half when he deserted his matrimonial home from 2015 to 2019 and then turned round to claim for the dissolution of the marriage based on desertion, and found that it is in fact, the respondent that can and should claim that the petitioner had deserted their matrimonial home for more than three (3) years. In *Ogunjobi v Ogunjobi*,²⁸ the court considered the issue of desertion and the court amongst other things held that a petitioner must plead and lead credible evidence to prove what constitutes desertion, that desertion remains a matter of fact and law to be determined by the court hearing the matter and that calculated moves or actions

to facilitate the dissolution of the said marriage is tantamount to using the law as an instrument of fraud.

Dowry

Dowry is the money, goods, or estate that a woman brings to her husband or his family in marriage. Most common in cultures that are strongly patrilineal and that expect women to reside with or near their husband's family (patrilocality), dowries have a long history in Europe, South Asia, Africa, and other parts of the world. In Nigeria, there has been a fusion of bride price and dowry as having the same meaning during a customary marriage ceremony. Strictly speaking, dowry is given a separate and prime place in traditional marriage ceremony in India. The underlying reason behind this obeisance is to protect the welfare of the bride in her matrimonial home, especially if the bride comes from a family that is well to do and her parents do not wish her to go through hardship or discomfort as a result of her transitional movement into her husband home.

Proof of Customary Marriage

Proof of Customary Marriage by evidence of payment of bride price and parental consent of the bride's family will suffice.²⁹ The consent of the parties can of course be presumed by their cohabitation. In some other situations, evidence of knowledge of the union by the relations of the

²⁶Section 15 (2) Matrimonial Causes Act 1970, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004.

²⁷*Zaccheus v Zaccheus* (2024) LPELR 61847 (CA).

²⁸*Ogunjobi Victoria Babakemi v Ogunjobi Innakwe Chinyere* (2021) LPELR 52894 (CA).

²⁹*Nwanga v. Ubani* (2002) 1 SMC at 231.

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parties may also constitute proof of such a marriage, provided no objection is raised by the family members. Even where members of the family are not involved in the marriage, evidence of cohabitation by the parties may suffice to prove status of husband and wife, and as such the marriage is voidable until either of the party takes step to dissolve the union. In Yoruba Customary Law, proof of the cohabitation may take the form of the wife being escorted to the husband's home after the customary marriage. In *Beckley v. Abiodun*,³⁰ it was held that there must be a handing over ceremony between both families and the leading of the wife to the husband's home. In modern times this practice of handing over (which in fact is a means of establishing cohabitation) occurs once the marriage formalities are completed by the paying of the bride price and prayers are said for the couple by both families who are present at the ceremony. The bride is handed over to members of the husband's family usually the female members. She is then taken away by the members of the husband's family to the husband's home. This may be his own personal home or the extended family home. It must be emphasized that this practice is an essential ingredient of customary marriage only in so far as it goes towards the issue of cohabitation and its absence does not invalidate the marriage once there is proof of cohabitation. Indeed, the

practice is designed to demonstrate that the parties have started cohabiting from the date the bride is taken to husband's home.

In customary marriages there is a recent trend to exchange rings like in statutory marriages. Although this has not sufficiently evolved to become a mandatory requirement of customary marriage, it can be further evidence of the parties' intention to enter into such a marriage. These various stages and processes of customary marriage, are generally similar in Nigeria. The effect of such compliance is merely of social and not of legal significance. Accordingly, the exchange of rings by the parties evidenced by the photograph and accepted as having occurred at a ceremony at the petitioner's family home, accords with the existence of a ceremony of customary marriage than any other ceremony. Other requirements include: ineligibility of a party to an existing statutory marriage or monogamous marriage to contract a customary marriage, ascertainment that parties are not related by consanguinity and affinity, payment of bride price, and leading of the bride to the house of the bridegroom or his parents.³¹

Existence of Customary and Statutory Marriages

As stated above, customary marriage is governed by customary law and is exclusively within the legislative competence of the state governments. These customary marriages are potentially

³⁰(1943) 17 NLR 59.

³¹See generally, E.I. Nwogugu, 2011. Family Law in Nigeria.

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polygamous with no prescribed limit as to the number of wives a man may validly marry, though the wives (or each wife) can be married to only one husband at any given time. On the other hand, the Marriage Act³² regulates statutory marriage, this form of marriage is essentially monogamous and it is within the exclusive legislative list of the Federal Government of Nigeria. Under this system, a man who is married to a woman is prohibited from entering into another form of marriage be it customary or statutory with another woman during the subsistence of the first marriage.

Thus, these two systems of marriage are incompatible with one another, although they have operated side by side in Nigeria for over a hundred years without a clash, at least from the legal point of view. The Marriage Act,³³ provides:

A statutory marriage is void where either of the parties to it is already married by the native law or custom to any person other than the person with whom the statutory marriage is being contracted.

Going by this provision, one can literally interpret this section to mean that if Mr. A married Miss B under the Act, but had been married to Miss C under native law and custom,

then the marriage to Miss B is void. Also, the Matrimonial Causes Decree 1970³⁴ states:

A statutory marriage is void where either of the parties is, at the time of the marriage, lawfully married to some other person.

Accordingly, it is crystal clear that there is legal parity as to the validity of competing customary marriage and statutory marriage. The determining factor is the first in time. This is in consonance with the maxim of equity that where equities are equal the first in time, prevails. Thus, the Marriage Act prohibits supervening effects of a particular brand of marriage over another. Therefore, once a man has contracted a valid marriage be it customary or statutory, he cannot during the existence of such a marriage contract a different form of marriage with a third person.

In effect, the Marriage Act³⁵ prohibits a man already married under customary law from marrying another person under the Act while the customary marriage subsists. In the same vein, the Act³⁶ prohibits a man who is married under the Act from contracting a valid marriage under native law and custom during the continuance of the statutory marriage. It states that:

Any person who is married under this Act ... shall be incapable during the continuance of such marriage, of contracting a valid marriage under

³²Marriage Act of 1914

³³Section 33(1) of the Marriage Act, Cap. 218 Laws of Federation of Nigeria, 1990

³⁴Section 3(1)(a) of the Matrimonial Causes Decree 1970

³⁵Section 33 of the Marriage Act, Cap. 218 Laws of Federation of Nigeria, 1990

³⁶Section 35

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native law or custom; but save as aforesaid nothing in this Act contained shall affect the validity of any marriage contracted under or in accordance with customary law, or in any manner apply to marriages so contracted.³⁷

The effect of violating these provisions makes whatever subsequent marriage(s) conducted to be null and void. The penalty for either of the two cases is imprisonment for five years under the Marriage Act.³⁸ From the foregoing, there is harmonized punishment of five years term of imprisonment provisions of the two sections, though two separate offences have been committed. Ijalaye has exemplified these two positions in this way:

Section 47 deals with the offence which may be described as marrying by the wrong method, since the man has the capacity to take a second wife by customary law. In the case of section 48, we have the offence analogous to bigamy. This offence may be described as the offence of taking another wife when there is no capacity to do so by any means.³⁹

It is obvious that by these provisions, the Marriage Act does not desire the mixing of the two systems, the intentions of the drafters of the Act seem to suggest that a party, more particularly a man, since he is the one capable of contracting two seemingly subsisting marriages

must make up his mind under which of the two systems he wants to marry, if he chooses customary system he has capacity to marry as several wives as possible and where he ventures into the realm of statutory marriage, he must be prepared to abide with the tenets that this is a union of one man and one woman to the exclusion of all others as defined by Lord Penzance in *Hyde v. Hyde*⁴⁰ Within the realm of Nigerian law, a man and a woman can be validly married under the Statute and under customary law at the same time.

Conversion of Customary Marriage to Statutory Marriage

Under customary law, a man is entitled to contract customary marriage at first with a woman and thereafter contracts another customary marriage with a second woman. This is an essential feature of customary law marriage whereby a man enjoys legal freedom to have plurality of wives under this system and each marriage is intended to exist for life. Therefore, where a man is married under customary law and contracts a subsequent statutory marriage which fails to comply with the essential and formality of such statutory marriage or where the said statutory marriage is defective, whatever legal status that such a man intends to confer on the spouse of that marriage will be of no effect based

³⁷ibid

³⁸Sections 47 and 48

³⁹D. A. Ijalaye, *Marriage Laws in Nigeria – Harmonization or Unification?* *The Nigerian Bar Journal* Vol. XII 1974: 21 – 31 @ 27).

⁴⁰1866 LR 1 P & D 130.

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on the principle that one cannot put something on nothing and expect it to stand. The position of customary law is that all wives of a man under customary marriages have equal status and that any purported choice or preference by a man to accord special status on any of the wives through the celebration of the statutory marriage either in the Registry or in the Church is of no effect whatsoever, except and of course, if he has divorced all other wives contracted under customary marriage. In other words, if a man contracts a customary marriage with the first woman and thereafter enters into statutory marriage with the same woman and later on contracts a customary marriage with a second woman, if it is established that the purported statutory marriage with the first wife does not exist or invalid, then what remains with the marriage with the first woman is that of customary marriage and accordingly the second customary marriage with the second woman remains valid.

The Nigerian Marriage Act makes provision for the conversion of customary marriage to statutory marriage so that if a man marries a woman under customary, he can later remarry the same woman under the statute.⁴¹ But there is no similar provision for the conversion of a marriage under the Act into a customary law

marriage. It is a common practice among Nigerian men of social standings to have many wives and there have been instances where men already married under the statutes took additional wives under the customary law without dissolving their earlier statutory marriage, a practice that is unlawful and void. This practice, though is an apparent breach of the law does not make such a practice lawful. It represents a common breach of the law.⁴²

Conversion is a process whereby a marriage is changed from its original form into another. In Private International Law, this process is called 'Mutability of Marriage,' an arrangement that can be done in several ways, but under Municipal law in Nigeria, there is only one type of conversion that is legally permissible and this is, the conversion of customary marriage into a statutory marriage. It is therefore, possible to convert a customary marriage only by the parties remarrying one another and not in any other way. In our opinion, the rationale behind this singular method of conversion is because the Marriage Act was passed for the purpose of encouraging monogamy and it cannot therefore allow a monogamous union to be converted into

⁴¹See *Ohochuku v Ohochuku* (1961) 1 All ER 253.

⁴²See Okay Achike: *Judicial Approach to Defects in Marriages Ceremonies in Nigeria*, in the Nigerian Law Journal

vol. 5, 1971 @141. See also Prof. A.B. Kasunmu: *The Law of Husband and Wife in Western Nigeria*, Integration of Customary and Modern Legal Systems in Africa University of Ife Press 1971.

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a potentially polygamous union by virtue of the Marriage Act.⁴³

Legal Elements of Conversion

In order to establish that conversion has taken place, there must be a valid marriage under the Act. This implies that the entire essential requirements of a valid marriage under the Act must have been complied with; otherwise, the purported conversion remains a mere charade or ceremony within the eyes of law. Jadesola Akande remarked thus:

It is common among Christian couples to perform the ceremony required by customary law and then follow this up with a religious service in a place of worship. By this they then believe has converted their marriage into a statutory one. But the solemnization of the ceremony in a church or chapel is not the only requirement, if at all it is one of the requirements, of a valid marriage under the Act ...⁴⁴

The general preponderance of opinions of jurists on Nigerian family law is that a customary marriage ceases to exist as soon as the statutory marriage has taken place and that the customary

marriage no longer exists in fact and in law.⁴⁵ The general consensus of opinions among these eminent jurists is that under Nigerian family law, this situation leads to the conclusion that the customary marriage and all conferred matrimonial rights fizzle out; so that the right to a refund of the dowry on dissolution of the statutory marriage is extinct.

The Law and Practice of Double-Decker Marriage

The practice of double-decker marriage is more of a Nigerian phenomenon which evolved from the operation of different systems of marriages among different cultures, religious and societies within legal system. A marriage becomes a double-decker whenever there exists a valid marriage and another marriage is now superimposed on the existing one, and this subsequent marriage is recognized as valid too. This view was judicially backed up in *Akparanta v. Akparanta*.⁴⁶ Invariably, the trial judge acknowledged the practice of “double Marriage” and held that each was distinct and independent of the other. The Court however, noted that “whether or not the parties intended a

⁴³Section 35. See also the case of *R v. Princewell* (1963) NMLR 54.

⁴⁴Jadesola O. Akande, *Laws and Customs Affecting Women's Status in Nigeria*, Lagos: International Federation of Women Lawyers, Nigeria, 1979 p.17.

⁴⁵See I.O. Agbede Recognition of Double Marriages in Nigeria Law 1968 17 ICLQ 735; D.A. Ijalaye Capacity to Marry under Nigerian Customary Law, *Nigerian Bar Journal* 1967 Vol. 3, pg. 20; Itse Sagay: *Multiple Marriages in Nigeria – A Conflict*

of Law with Culture, NBJ Vol. XII 1974 pg. 82; A.B. Kasunmu The Matrimonial Causes Decree 1970: A Critical Analysis, *Nigerian Journal of Contemporary Law* Vol. 2 No. 1 pg. 98; Akande, Legal Problems of Converting Customary Marriage into a Statutory Marriage in Nigeria, being a paper presented at the National Conference on Marriage Laws in Nigeria, held at the Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 1981.

⁴⁶(1972) 2 ECCLR 779

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monogamous marriage is a question for an objective answer depending on the evidence.”⁴⁷ Although this viewpoint appears to be a minority opinion among jurists in Nigeria, yet Olatunbosun shares the view and pungently canvassed⁴⁸ that whenever the status of marriage conducted in a foreign country is being considered in a divorce proceeding by a municipal court of the land, the court will only have capacity to terminate a marriage which is recognized in her country. Under conflict of laws situations, the nature of marriage is determined by the Lex Loci Celebrations and the two requirements whether the union conforms to the English notion of marriage are that the union is potentially for an indefinite period and to the exclusion of all other persons. Although the second requirement of exclusion of all other persons have been criticized as not being a proper basis to disregard the status of husband and wife conferred on parties to a potentially polygamous form of marriage. Accordingly, the determination of the nature of the marriage is no longer of importance in deciding whether the parties are entitled to matrimonial relief from the English Courts. In fact, the new trend in both common law and civil law countries in modern

times is the universal recognition of status created by the legal system that is competent to do so, though the same legal effect may not be given to all the incidents of such status. The above-stated proposition was enunciated in the Locus Classicus case of *Ohochuku v. Ohochuku*⁴⁹ where the parties who were Nigerians had married in accordance with customary law in Nigeria in 1949. They subsequently went through a marriage ceremony in London in 1953. In 1959, the wife petitioned for divorce on the ground of cruelty. It was held that it could not grant a decree of divorce of the first marriage but the court dissolved the second marriage. The learned Judge Wrangham J. rhetorically asked, “The only question is: What marriage is it that has to be dissolved? Apparently ignoring the polygamous marriage contracted by the parties at the date of their first marriage, proceeded to dissolve the second marriage celebrated in England by virtue of S.18 (1) (b) of the English Matrimonial Causes Act 1950 having found in the wife’s favour on the issue of cruelty. It is clear that the learned Judge in *Ohochuku’s* case did not accept the view that the second marriage ceremony changed the character of the marriage; rather it created a second marriage. Incidentally,

⁴⁷ibid at 786.

⁴⁸A. I. Olatunbosun, ‘Double-Decker Marriage in Private International Law: A Dialectical Appraisal’ in *Indian Society of International Law New Delhi* Vol. 4, No. 1 Jan – March 2004: 139 –159, see also E. Ijalana, and J. Agbana, (2021) A Critical Appraisal of the Concept of Double-Decker Marriage under the Nigerian Family Law.

Beijing Law Review, 12, 1163-1178. doi:

[10.4236/blr.2021.124060](https://doi.org/10.4236/blr.2021.124060).

Onyekachi Eni, Ph.D, Towards the Decolonization of Nigeria’s Matrimonial Regimen: A Socio-Legal Appraisal of Double-decker Marriage System in *AJLHR* 4 (2) 2020.

⁴⁹(1960) 1 WLR 183

Professor Adeniyi Olatunbosun, SAN and Dr. Temilade O. Jolaosho

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the decision of the learned Judge established the fact that ‘double-decker marriage’ is acknowledged in England between foreigners whose law of domicile permits the co-existence of polygamous and monogamous forms of marriages.

Choice of Nature of Marriage

In Nigeria, different systems of marriage exist, while it is left for an individual to cherry pick which type suits him/ her best, fully aware of the incidents of each.⁵⁰ But there can be no mixing of the two. You cannot be validly married under the statute and under customary law at the same time, unless it is to the same person. This is what has been described as ‘Double-decker Marriage’ especially where one of the two marriages, i.e. statutory marriage is contracted outside Nigeria. Although some notable jurists have argued that a subsequent statutory after a valid customary marriage between the same parties converts a prior customary marriage and thereby the first marriage ceases to exist. Also, some scholars have argued that it is even doubtful whether there can be a valid subsequent customary marriage between the two parties already statutorily married.

Nevertheless, we are of the opinion that such a position is not doubtful in the sense that the subsequent customary marriage is more of a

social and cultural status without any objective of creating a new legal status on the already existing legal status created by the earlier statutory marriage and we submit that this practice is more cosmetic than legalistic. This situation is more applicable where parties concerned enter into a statutory marriage without the intention of following it up with celebration for various reasons known to them but later on inform their relations of the new development, leading to the celebration of a customary marriage.

Consequently, the following attitude was envisaged under the Marriage Act. If Mr. X is about to get married, he must first consider whether he intends to have one wife at a time all his life, or might want more than one at any one time. If he is the type who prefers monogamy, then he may (but not necessarily) contract a statutory marriage. He may also of course contract a customary marriage, and then limit himself to one wife under that system. A customary marriage can in fact be de facto (but not de jure) monogamous, although it is potentially polygamous. However, if after contracting the statutory marriage, Mr. X meets another woman who he is determined to marry then he must get a dissolution of his first marriage before he can marry the second woman. If on the other hand Mr. X prefers

⁵⁰Kasunmu & Salacuse: *Nigerian Family Law* (1966). Olawale Ajai & Toyi Ipaye (Mrs.): *Rights of Women and Children in Divorce* (1997), Friedrich Ebert Foundation. I.E. Sagay: *Family Law in Nigeria* (1999) Malthouse

Books. I.E. Sagay: *Case Law under the Matrimonial Decree* (1976) Obi: *Modern Family Law in Nigeria* (1966) Sweet and Maxwell.

Professor Adeniyi Olatunbosun, SAN and Dr. Temilade O. Jolaosho

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polygamy, he must marry under customary law. Should he later meet a woman whom for some odd reason, he desires to marry under the statute, then he must dissolve all his customary marriages before he can marry the new woman statutorily? Unfortunately, things have not worked out so smoothly in Nigeria. A man already married under customary law to one woman, nevertheless goes ahead and ‘marries’ another woman under the statute. Even more widespread are the cases of men already married to one woman under the statute, going on to ‘marry’ several other wives under customary law. The reasons for this vary.

Initially it may be that an impecunious young man, may be satisfied with one wife, but as he grows older and more affluent, he not only desires variety, but can afford variety. Matters are not helped much by the insistence of educated Nigerian girls on statutory marriage which they believe, guarantees them the security and right of exclusive possession not available in customary marriage. The men themselves do not as a general rule bother to dissolve their prior marriages because of the time, labour and expenses involved, and also probably because they are still strongly attached to their first wives. This has resulted in the concept of an institution of the ‘Madam’ or “wearer of the ring” (a literal translation of a Yoruba expression) or the ‘legal wife’ and a proliferation of other ‘wives’ living in

hired apartments.⁵¹ In *Okafor & Ors. v Okafor & Anor*,⁵² the issue for determination was whether a person who is married under the Marriage Act can contract a valid marriage under customary law with another woman. The court found that late Chief Clement Okafor contracted a statutory marriage with the 1st plaintiff on December 30 1967 but thereafter wanted to contract a subsequent customary marriage with another woman. The court held that any subsequent alleged marriage, customary or otherwise between the late Chief Clement Okafor and any other woman during his statutory marriage to the 1st plaintiff was rendered invalid, null and void by operation of law.

Parties to a marriage must at all times be guided by the law. Worthy of mention is the conflict of law rule which permits a man who is married under customary law to subsequently marry under statutory law and where the nature of the marriage is being determined in a foreign land, the foreign court is entitled to classify the two systems of marriage contracted by the man as a form of double-decker marriage. In the event where issues arise and the parties are seeking dissolution, such marriage whether statutory or customary, is not dissolved by effluxion of time. It is not enough for either party to a marriage to bring it to an end by merely deposing to an affidavit to that effect.

Potentially Polygamous Marriage

⁵¹See Itse Sagay: *Multiple Marriages in Nigeria – A Conflict of Law with Culture*, Nigerian Bar Journal vol. XII 1974 p. 82.

⁵²*Okafor & Ors v Okafor & Anor* (2022) LPELR- 59136 (CA).

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A marriage is potentially polygamous though in fact monogamous if a husband is entitled by the law that determines the nature of his marriage to take a plurality of wives, his marriage is considered to be polygamous notwithstanding that at the time when the question is raised, he has not exercised that right nor ever intends to. If the marriage is potentially polygamous at its inception then, though it may be possible to change it into a monogamous marriage, it retains its polygamous nature until such change is actually made. For example, if A's marriage to B in the year 2021 is prefaced by a customary marriage with the said B and it is proved that the statutory marriage conducted in 2021 is null and void, then what remains between A and B is that of a customary law marriage which to all intents and purposes, allows for multiple marriages by A with other women. Therefore, the said statutory marriage of 2021 would not constitute a bar to the capacity of A to marrying any subsequent wife. In the light of the foregoing analysis above, it can be said that the first customary marriage between A and B permits A to enter into customary court marriage with B and that the statutory marriage of 2021 by A with B if found to be valid would not constitute a 'double-decker marriage.' So also the second customary

marriage between A and B does not constitute a double-decker marriage between them. In fact, the general principle of private international law is to the effect that every marriage is potentially monogamous or polygamous upon the proof of the existence of certain factors.⁵³

Child of the Marriage

The Matrimonial Causes Act⁵⁴ provides:

Without prejudice to the operation of subsection (1) of this section in other respects, a decree of nullity under this Act of a voidable marriage shall not render illegitimate a child of the parties born since, or legitimated during the marriage.

This section is also in conformity with the 1979 Constitution⁵⁵ re-enacted in the 1999 Constitution⁵⁶ which provides that:

No citizen of Nigeria shall be subjected to any disability deprivation merely by reason of the circumstances of his birth.

Accordingly, the Child of the Marriage, could not have been illegitimate even if the Parties had not been married. Under Nigerian law, a child could only be legitimated upon the subsequent marriage of the parents.⁵⁷ The authors are not aware of any ceremony, whether prior to the 1979 Constitution or afterwards, where a father acknowledges paternity of his child, more so an unborn child. The only ceremony which exists is

⁵³See I. O. Agbede, *Themes on Conflict of Laws*, Shanneson, Ibadan, Nigeria (1989). See also P. M. North, J. J. Fawcett: *Cheshire and North's Private International Law*, Butterworths 12th ed., (1992) London, Dublin, Edinburgh.

⁵⁴Section 38 (2)

⁵⁵Section 39 (2)

⁵⁶Section 42 (2)

⁵⁷See Section 3(1) Legitimacy Act.

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a naming ceremony of the child and this usually takes place at the home of the father, or in the event that the parents are unmarried at the home of a relation of the father or a neutral venue. It is inconceivable that any Yoruba man would name his child at the home of the child's maternal grandparents, much less go through any elaborate ceremony. A father acknowledges paternity of his child when he names the child. Moreover, it is not possible that any such naming ceremony would involve an exchange of rings by the parents of such child whether born or unborn.

Nullity of Marriage

By virtue of the Matrimonial Causes Act,⁵⁸ a petition under this Act for nullity of marriage may be based on the ground that the marriage is void, or on the ground that the marriage is voidable at the suit of the petitioner. A decree of nullity under this Act⁵⁹ of a voidable marriage shall annul the marriage from and including the date on which the decree becomes absolute.

The Matrimonial Causes Act⁶⁰ states that a marriage will be void in the following circumstances:

(1) subject to the provisions of this section, a marriage that takes place after the

commencement of this Act is void in any of the following cases but not otherwise, that is to say, where –

(a) Either of the parties is, at the time of the marriage, lawfully married to some other person.

Further, as previously stated, the Marriage Act⁶¹ provides that a person married under the Act shall be incapable of contracting a valid marriage under customary law, and therefore such later customary marriage will be void. If indeed it is established that the Respondent was validly married to the Petitioner by virtue of a statutory marriage as opposed to a customary marriage, then the ceremonies of marriage with the Petitioner will result in those later ceremonies of marriage being void and subject to a Decree of Nullity pursuant to the Matrimonial Causes Act.⁶²

Marriage by Cohabitation and Repute

Nigerian law recognizes marriage by cohabitation and repute. Once there has been a ceremony of marriage which is invalid for some reason the parties can be found to have been married if they can show cohabitation and repute. In *Nickaf v Nickaf*,⁶³ the Court of Appeal, Kaduna, held that there could be marriage by

⁵⁸Section 34 of the Matrimonial Causes Act,⁵⁸ Cap 220, Laws of Federation 1990

⁵⁹*ibid.* Section 38 (1)

⁶⁰Section 3 (1).

⁶¹Section 35.

⁶²Section 34 and 38.

⁶³Suit No. CA/1E/79/84. (Unreported) Court of Appeal, Kaduna; Akpata J.C.A observed that the payment of bride price is an essential requirement of marriage under customary law of most communities in Nigeria. See also E.I. Nwogugu, *Family Law in Nigeria* (Heinemann, 1990) 56-58. E.I. Nwogugu: *Family Law in Nigeria*, Revised Edition (2001) (Heinemann Educational Books (Nigeria) Plc.

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cohabitation and repute in Nigeria. This decision further buttresses the fact that customary law marriage evolves with contemporary challenges of the time since customary law marriage requires evidence of payment of dowry or bride price, capacity to marry each other by the parties and the handing over of the bride by the parents. However, where the parties to the marriage are adults with requisite capacities, Nigerian courts are ready to accord the status of customary law marriage on the parties provided the parties are persons of repute and have substantially lived together as husband and wife by cohabitation. This is to further support our position above that customary law marriage is adaptable to modern trends and the nature of the marriage will be accorded recognition once the parties concerned have produced evidence to substantiate their intentions.

The question of waiver of bride price was canvassed in *Nickaf v Nickaf*.⁶⁴ In that case, the plaintiff Mrs. Nickaf sued her husband, Mr. Nickaf, for libel which was in the form of a disclaimer of their marriage published in a national newspaper. Both parties came from Kagoro in Kaduna State. The plaintiff and her father averred that the respondent asked for her hand in marriage. Both plaintiff and her father consented to the request. No bride price was paid or demanded nor was there a traditional marriage ceremony. Evidence was given for the

plaintiff's case that bride price is not always necessary in Kagoro custom. It only becomes necessary when the girl's parents demanded it. On the other hand, witnesses for the respondent claimed that the payment of bride price and the marriage ceremony are vital for a valid marriage. The learned trial judge of the court of first instance found that a valid customary marriage subsisted between the parties and that the newspaper publication constituted a libel. On appeal, the learned counsel for the plaintiff/ respondent in dealing with the non-payment of bride price contended that the beneficiary of a right or benefit under a marriage contract could waive it completely or partially. Akpata, J.C.A. observed that there was no evidence from the defense on whether bride price could be waived under Kagoro custom. He found that the payment of bride price is an essential requirement of marriage under customary law of most communities in Nigeria and observed that "where native law and custom forbids a waiver of any ingredient of marriage, a waiver of it would render the marriage void." In the opinion of the learned judge, bride price is an "indispensable consideration" in some parts of the country. Unfortunately, he did not reach a final decision on this issue but concluded that "the appellant has not established that the marriage between himself and the respondent was not valid." The right to the bride price is not only that of a father

⁶⁴Suit No. CA/1E/79/84. (Unreported) Court of Appeal, Kaduna.

Professor Adeniyi Olatunbosun, SAN and Dr. Temilade O. Jolaosho

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but also some members of his nuclear family. The interest of this group cannot be readily waived. On the whole, however, complete waiver of bride price is unusual. Some families merely ask the suitor for a token payment rather than grant outright waiver.

Summary of Law and Practice on Customary Marriage

From the foregoing, it is established that by operation of law, customary marriage is a recognized system of marriage in Nigeria and that every Nigerian who wishes is entitled to contract marriage under this system. By prevailing practice, customary marriage may be contracted by the willing parties and later follow-up by a statutory marriage provided the statutory marriage is contracted with the same parties. Every customary marriage has legal parity with statutory marriage under the Nigerian law. And that for a proof of customary marriage the parties must possess capacity, payment of bride price and handing over of the bride to the groom; that cohabitation by repute is a recognized form of proof of customary marriage; that a man who is married under customary law marriage is obliged to contract a statutory marriage with the same woman under the Marriage Act; that a man who contracts a customary marriage and later on converts the nature of the marriage to a monogamous marriage is prevented from contracting either a customary marriage or a statutory marriage with another woman. Under the Nigerian Family Law, a party to the marriage

has a choice as to the system of marriage that would govern his way of life, there is no mixing of two systems of marriage except with the same spouse. If a man contracts a customary marriage with a first woman and later contracts a statutory marriage with that first woman but the statutory marriage is defective or does not exist in law, the nature of his marriage amounts to a customary form of marriage; therefore, that whoever contracts a customary marriage as the husband is allowed under the law to contract subsequent marriages with other women; that where a man contracts a customary marriage and later on contracts a valid statutory marriage, this constitutes a bar to subsequent marriages with other women; however, a man who has contracted a customary marriage may be permitted to contract a statutory marriage with the same woman and within the conflict of law principles, the statutory marriage automatically converts a prior customary marriage to that of monogamous marriage. Nevertheless, the conflict of law rules permit a man who is married under customary law to subsequently marry under statutory law and where the nature of the marriage is being determined in a foreign land, the foreign court is entitled to classify the two systems of marriage contracted by the man as a form of double-decker marriage.

Conclusion

Generally, requirements for valid marriage under customary law differ from one community to the other; there are some common

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denominators that have been highlighted above. For instance, parties must have capacity to marry; even though a particular age is not prescribed, it is generally believed that parties must have attained puberty. This is however not a sacrosanct rule. Thus, a number of legislations have emerged to fix the minimum age for customary law marriage. Another requirement is the consent of parties and parents. For the parties, whenever they are capable of expressing their consent to the marriage, such consent is expressly demanded and obtained before the marriage. Where they are not capable of expressing their consent or understanding the consequences of giving it, such consent can be withdrawn after marriage. Due to the communal intricacies associated with customary marriage, parental consent is either deemed necessary or mandatory.

Professor Adeniyi Olatunbosun, SAN and Dr. Temilade O. Jolaosho